

An improved method for the determination of manganese in rocks, minerals, ores, soils, steel, alloys, sea-bed polymetallic nodules and environmental samples including water and effluents

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Abstract : A highly useful and reliable extraction spectrophotometric method has been developed for the determination of manganese in a wide variety of samples having complex matrices based upon reaction system of Mn(II)-2,3-dihydroxynaphthalene, an O-O' type of ligand forming an anionic complex with manganese, irrespective of its valence states, which is readily extractable as a purple ion-pair complex into methyl-isobutyl ketone (MIBK) under the influence of a cationic surfactant, cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB). The only interference of iron has been successfully eliminated by its prior extraction with methyl-isobutyl ketone (MIBK). The method is robust as is evidenced by its application to a wide variety of samples of diverse matrices, including certified reference materials. While most spectrophotometric methods, including formaldoxime, pyridil-azo-naphthol and the well known permanganate method fail when applied to samples of complex matrices, developed method by us yields highly accurate results as attested by those obtained from AAS as well as by certified/recommended values CRMs.

Keywords : Solvent extraction, spectrophotometry, 2,3-dihydroxynaphthalene, cetyltrimethyl ammonium bromide, manganese, liquid-liquid extraction, rock.

Introduction

There are innumerable spectrophotometric methods for the determination of manganese¹, including the ones using the reagents, formaldoxime², pyridylazonaphthol³, PAR⁴, TAN⁵, TAR⁶, etc. However, when applied to different geological samples of diverse matrices, none of these could yield satisfactory results. This prompted us to develop a suitable spectrophotometric method based upon a novel reaction scheme for application to geological samples.

Recently we have reported an useful extraction spectrophotometric method for the determination of manganese in rocks, minerals, plant ash and soil samples based upon the reaction of Mn(II) with the reagent, 2,3-dihydroxynaphthalene and CTAB⁷. In this method Mn(II) forms an anionic chelate with the cited reagent (2,3-H₂ND) under appropriate reaction conditions. This anionic chelate is extracted as an intense purple coloured ion-pair complex with CTAB at a pH above 8 (8-10) into ethylacetate. The absorbance of the colour was measured

at 547 nm. The molar absorptivity of this system being $1.2 \times 10^4 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. This method requires prior removal of iron because it seriously interferes in the determination of manganese. An extractive method was suggested for elimination of iron prior to the determination of Mn. Fe(III) similarly forms reddish orange anionic chelate with the reagent (2,3-H₂ND) and the same gets extracted into ethylacetate as an ion pair complex with CTAB over a pH range 4-10. Unless iron is removed, it seriously interferes in the determination of Mn. In the method reported, we have eliminated iron by its prior extraction as an ion-pair of Fe(III)-2,3-H₂ND anionic complex with CTA⁺ at pH 4-5. However, if the content of iron is very high (>10%), double extraction was required, and in some of the cases interference of iron could not be completely eliminated, and at the same time some loss of manganese was also observed. This aspect has now been fully taken care of by completely eliminating iron irrespective of its content in the sample, by a single extraction using MIBK in hydrochloric acid medium. Prior to the

determination of manganese other than iron, no interference was encountered in the determination of manganese in any type of sample. The results obtained for manganese determination in the above mentioned type of samples compared favourably with those obtained from AAS. The results obtained by the proposed method was also compared with those obtained by formaldoxime and pyridil-azo-naphthol methods. However, the latter two methods failed to yield the desired results as obtained from AAS and the proposed method due to serious interference of accompanying ions in the sample matrices. The present paper encompasses a systematic study on the application of the proposed method to a host of rock, soil, minerals, steel, alloys, water and environmental samples.

Experimental

Apparatus :

Spectrophotometer [Analytikjena (Germany) make instrument having model No. specord 250/plus] was used for absorbance measurements. pH meter, make Elico – L1-120 was used for pH measurements. Separating funnels – Separating funnels of 125 ml capacity were used for liquid-liquid extraction.

Reagents :

Manganese – 1 mg ml⁻¹ solution : Weighed 1.0 g of metallic manganese in 50 ml 1 : 1 HNO₃ and diluted to 1 litre. Iron – 1 mg ml⁻¹ solution : Weighed 1.7553 g of (NH₄)₂SO₄.FeSO₄.6H₂O in distilled water and diluted, added 10 ml of H₂SO₄ and finally diluted it to 250 ml in a calibrated 250 ml volumetric flask. 2,3-Dihydroxy-naphthalene, Flucka make (98.5% pure) : A 0.1% (m/v) solution in MIBK was prepared. Ammonia solution. Cetyltrimethylammonium bromide.

Procedure :

The estimation of manganese was carried out in three steps which are as under.

Dissolution of samples :

For rocks, soils, minerals and sea-bed polymetallic nodules :

A 0.5 g ground (~200 mesh) sample was taken in a Teflon beaker and ~1.0 g NH₄HF₂ and ~5.0 ml of HNO₃ were added. Heated the contents on a hot plate for 2–3 h. Repeated heating with another 1.0 g of NH₄HF₂ and 5 ml HNO₃. After the contents of the Teflon beaker

got dried, added 10 ml of conc. HCl and heated till dryness. Repeated the HCl treatment two times. Added ~15–20 ml distilled water and digested for 30 min. Transferred the solution into a 250 ml beaker and added a further 50 ml distilled water and ~5 ml HCl. Boiled the solution, cooled and filtered. Transferred the solution to a 100 ml vol. flask and made up the volume to 100 ml.

For steel and alloys samples :

Weighed about 0.5 g of steel samples (taken exact weight) into a 250 ml beaker, and to it added 10 ml of 2 : 1 HCl. Mixed well and then heated on a hot plate till complete dissolution of the sample took place. If the sample was not completely attacked, added another 2 : 1 HCl and heated.

Once the sample was completely dissolved, cooled the solution and then transferred into a 100 ml calibrated volumetric flask and made up the volume to the mark.

Separation of iron :

Taken about 5–10 ml aliquot of sample into a 100 ml beaker and made 6 mol L⁻¹ by adding hydrochloric acid and transferred to a 125 ml separating funnel. A 10 ml methyl-isobutyl ketone (MIBK) was added to the solution, shaken well for 3–4 min. Iron got extracted completely into MIBK. Manganese remained in the aqueous solution, discarded the organic layer containing iron.

Separation of titanium :

Transferred aqueous solution obtained from above section into a 125 separating funnel and to it added ~0.1 g 2,3-H₂ND and mixed well. To it added 10 ml of 60% (m/v) sodium acetate followed by 10 ml of MIBK. Shaken the mixture for ~2 min. Allowed for phase separation. Discarded the organic layer containing yellowish-orange chelate of Ti(OH)³⁺-2,3-H₂ND complex. The aqueous layer was stored for the determination of manganese.

Spectrophotometric measurements :

The aqueous layer obtained from the above section was transferred to a 125 ml separating funnel, a 0.1 g solid 2,3-dihydroxynaphthalene was added to it, mixed well and a 10 ml MIBK was added to it. Maintained the pH ~10 by adding dil ammonia dropwise and then a 0.1 g CTAB was added to it.

Shaken for 2–3 min, allowed for phase separation. Manganese as distinct purple coloured ion pair complex

got extracted into MIBK. After 15 min the absorbance of the complex in MIBK was measured at 547 nm against the reagent blank.

Results and discussion

Except Atomic Absorption and ICP-AES, which are not always available in all the laboratories for the determination of manganese at trace to percentage level, no spectrophotometric method, including those reported with permanganate, formaldoxime, pyridil-azo-naphthol *etc.* is known to yield satisfactory results for its determination owing to interferences of many ions like iron, vanadium, copper, cobalt *etc.* As has been stated in the earlier paper⁷ the 2,3-dihydroxynaphthalene-manganese system is almost free from interferences of most matrix elements except iron which is a serious interferent. While applying the method to silicate rocks, soils, water and other samples, iron was removed by liquid-liquid extraction with 2,3-dihydroxynaphthalene at a pH 4–5 prior to the determination of manganese. Although the method was found suitable for application to these types of samples, it sometimes yielded unsatisfactory results in terms of accuracy when applied to samples like steel and high iron bearing minerals. This was due to the fact that from these sample solutions iron could not be satisfactorily removed by prior extraction of Fe-2,3-H₂ND complex into ethyl acetate at pH 4–5. Sometimes, double to triple extractions are needed for iron removal which are obviously time consuming. This tedious process has been replaced by an alternative convenient technique of liquid-liquid extraction using methyl-isobutyl ketone (MIBK). In a single extraction, MIBK removes more than 95% (m/v) of iron from the sample solution leaving manganese in the aqueous solution. From the aqueous solution free from iron, manganese was selectively determined by spectrophotometry after extracting the purple Mn(II)-2,3-H₂ND complex into MIBK, and measuring the absorbance at 547 nm against reagent blank.

For the following studies 20 µg of Mn was extracted into 20 ml of MIBK.

Removal of iron by MIBK :

The well known procedure of extraction of iron by MIBK was adopted in the present case. Fe(III) forms an anionic complex FeCl_4^- in hydrochloric acid medium,

which is extracted as an ion pair complex using H^+ as a counter-cation into MIBK and thus iron was removed. We varied the concentration of HCl and found that atleast 6 mol L⁻¹ HCl was necessary for complete extraction of iron.

Effect of pH :

Effect of pH on the complex formation was studied in detail. pH of the reaction solution was varied over the range, 2 to 11. The colour starts forming at a pH above 6.0 and it gradually increases with the increase in pH upto pH 8.0. Thereafter, *i.e.* beyond pH 8.0 (8.0 to 11) it remains constant. Fig. 1 shows the effect of pH on the colour intensity of the extracted complex.

Fig. 1. Effect of pH on the colour intensity of the complex (Mn = 3.2 µg/ml).

Effect of reagent (2,3-dihydroxynaphthalene) concentration :

Under the optimized condition of pH, the concentration of 2,3-dihydroxynaphthalene was varied from 0.01 to 1.5% (m/v). A 0.1 g of solid reagent per 10 ml MIBK was found to be optimum (for attaining maximum sensitivity of the colour, $\epsilon = 1.2 \times 10^4 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$). Any further increase in the concentration of 2,3-dihydroxynaphthalene does not enhance the sensitivity further. Fig. 2 shows the effect of reagent (2,3-dihydroxynaphthalene) concentration on the intensity of complex formed.

Effect of concentration of cetyltrimethylammonium bromide :

Manganese, irrespective of its valence state reacts with

Fig. 2. Effect of the reagent (2,3-dihydroxynaphthalene) on the colour intensity of the complex (Mn = 3.2 $\mu\text{g/ml}$).

2,3-dihydroxynaphthalene at pH 8–10 forming instantaneously a pale yellowish green anionic complex on shaking. This anionic complex gets readily extracted into MIBK under the influence of a cationic surfactant, CTAB, displaying a distinct purple colour in MIBK medium. In order to study the effect of CTAB on the formation of the ion-pair complex (cetyltrimethylammonium ion acts as a counter cation in the formation of the ion-pair complex), its concentration was varied from 0.01 to 1.5% (m/v) in 10 ml of MIBK. Maximum sensitivity was observed with 0.1 g of cetyltrimethylammoniumbromide. Fig. 3 shows the effect of CTMB concentration on the colour intensity of the complex formed.

Fig. 3. Effect of CTAB (cetyltrimethylammonium bromide) on the colour intensity of the complex (Mn = 3.2 $\mu\text{g/ml}$).

Choice of solvents :

Solvents play a very crucial role in the extraction of metal complexes, particularly in enhancing the molar absorptivity/sensitivity of the coloured complexes. Accordingly, in our present study we have tried to extract the anionic complex of Mn-2,3- H_2ND using different solvents. The solvents chosen were ethyl/butyl/pentyl acetates, carbon tetrachloride, chloroform, benzene, xylene and MIBK (methyl-isobutyl ketone). Ethyl acetate and MIBK gave almost equivalent results in terms of sensitivity, selectivity and ease of extraction. However, owing to dual advantages of MIBK i.e. suitability as a solvent/reagent in the prior extractive elimination of iron as well as in maximizing absorbance of the complex extracted, MIBK was chosen as a solvent in the present study.

Beer's law, molar absorptivity, sensitivity and precision :

Beer's law was obeyed for determination of Mn followed by this method over a wide linear range from 0 to 10.0 ppm. The molar absorptivity and the Sandell's sensitivity of the method are worked out to be $1.2 \times 10^4 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.0045 \mu\text{g/cm}^2$ respectively. The precision of the method for 1 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ Mn concentration is 1% and in samples containing Mn from 0.1 to 1% (m/m), it is in the range, 2–3%.

Effect of diverse ions :

A host of ions accompanying Mn in natural rock, soil, stream sediment samples were studied on the determination of 10 $\mu\text{g}/10 \text{ ml}$ Mn spectrophotometrically. Cations like Fe, Cu, Co, Ni, Mo, V, Na, K, Rb, Sr, Ti, Nb, Ta etc. and anions like Cl^- , SO_4^{2-} , PO_4^{3-} , NO_3^- , I^- , Br^- and acetate were also studied. The tolerance limits of these ions have been shown in the Table 1. Iron which is always present in excess to Mn in most samples does interfere seriously. It is eliminated prior to the determination of Mn as per the procedure given.

Other ions which interfere when present in 10 fold excess to Mn are V and Cu. These ions can be removed if present in appreciable quantities by a prior solvent extraction at pH 4–5 using the same reagent (2,3-dihydroxynaphthalene) as their neutral complexes. However, in silicate rocks these ions at 10 fold excess concentration to Mn are seldom present. In the case of steel and alloy samples often V may be present and while estimating Mn in these samples a prior separation of V is resorted to.

Table 1. Effect of foreign ions on the determination of 1.0 mg L⁻¹ Mn

Sl. no.	Ions	Tolerance limit ^a (mg L ⁻¹)
1.	Al ³⁺ , Ba ²⁺ , Ca ²⁺ , Mg ²⁺ , Li ⁺ , Na ⁺ , K ⁺ , Rb ⁺ , NO ³⁻ , Cl ⁻ , Br ⁻ , I ⁻ , CH ₃ COO ⁻	1000
2.	Pb ²⁺ , Ta ⁵⁺ , Th ⁴⁺ , Ni ²⁺ , Zn ²⁺ , Sc ⁴⁺ , La ³⁺ , Sr ²⁺ , Sb ²⁺ , Cr ³⁺	100
3.	Bi ²⁺ , Cd ²⁺ , Ag ⁺ , Ce ²⁺ , Ti ⁴⁺ , PO ₄ ³⁻ , SO ₄ ²⁻	50
4.	Cu ²⁺ , Hg ²⁺ , W ⁶⁺ , V ⁵⁺ , Zr ⁴⁺ , Mo ⁵⁺ , U ⁶⁺ , Nb ⁵⁺ , F ⁻	10
5.	Fe ³⁺	5

^aFor <2% error.

concentration of cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB) gives a slope of 1.8, close to the integer 2, indicating that Mn²⁺ reacts with two moles of H₂ND.

Similar a slope of 2 was obtained for the plot of log D vs CTAB concentration, indicating that 2 moles of CTAB is required for the extraction of 1 mole of Mn²⁺.

Similarly, plot of log D vs pH shows a slope of 4, indicating that 4H⁺ atoms are released in the reaction. The eq. (5) can now be written as

$$\log K_{ex}(w,x) = \log D - 4 \text{pH} - 2 \log [\text{H}_2\text{ND}] - 2 \log \text{Q}^+$$

Thus the eq. (1) can be written :

Tentative stoichiometry of the complex formed :

The stoichiometry of the complex was found out by mole ratio method as well as by slope analysis⁸. In line with our earlier findings, the stoichiometry was found to be 1 : 2 : 2 (Mn : 2,3-H₂ND : CTAB).

The equilibrium reaction can be written as,

Assuming no side reaction, the equilibrium constant, K_{ex}(w,x) can be written as follows :

$$K_{ex}(w,x) = \frac{[\text{Q}_x^+ \{ \text{Mn}(\text{ND})_w^{(2-2w)} \}]_0}{[\text{Mn}^{2+}] [\text{H}_2\text{ND}]_0^w [\text{Q}^+]^x} \quad (2)$$

or,

$$K_{ex}(w,x) = D \frac{[\text{H}^+]^{2w}}{[\text{H}_2\text{ND}]_0^w [\text{Q}^+]^x} \quad (3)$$

where

$$D = \frac{[\text{Q}_x^+ \text{Mn}(\text{ND})_w^{(2-2w)}]_0}{[\text{Mn}^{2+}]} \quad (4)$$

Eq. (3) can be rewritten as

$$\log K_{ex}(w,x) = \log D - 2w\text{pH} - w \log [\text{H}_2\text{ND}]_0 - x \log [\text{Q}] \quad (5)$$

Plot of log D vs log [H₂ND] (slope analysis) at a constant

Tentative reaction scheme :

Analytical application :

The method developed in this laboratory was thoroughly applied to a number of silicate rocks, soils, stream sediments, minerals (sea-bed polymetallic nodules) and steel samples including a few certified reference samples. The results have been shown in Tables 2 and 3.

Table 2. Determination of manganese in silicate rocks, soils, minerals and plant ash (n = 3)

Sl. no.	Sample detail	Certified/ Recommended value % Mn	Proposed method % Mn	Flame AAS %Mn
1	Canmet SY-3	0.32	0.30	0.33
2	Canmet MRG-1	0.17	0.15	0.18
3	Euronorm-CRM No. 782-1 (Dolorite)	0.063	0.060	0.065
4	USGS Granodiorite, GSP-2	0.032	0.030	0.035
5	USGS Basalt, BHVO-2	0.1290	0.1285	0.130
6	BCS/SS No. 407/1 (low alloy steel)	0.047	0.045	0.042

Table-2 (contd.)

7	NML-standard No. 2388 (Ocean bed- polymetallic nodules)	21.28	21.41	21.30
8	Canmet SY-4	0.084	0.085	0.087
9	USGS Green River shale- SGR-1b	0.0267	0.027	0.026
10	USGS Diabase/ Dolerite-DNC-1a	0.116	0.120	0.116
11	USGS Diabase- W-2a	0.129	0.124	0.122
12	CANMET Calcareous C Horizon Soil-SO-3	0.052	0.050	0.048
13	CaNMET Chemogenic A Horizon Soil-SO-4	0.060	0.057	0.055
14	Charminar Cigarette- (Dry ash basis)		0.090	0.085

Table 3. Determination of manganese in water and effluent samples (n = 3)

Sample No.	Mn (mg/L)	
	Proposed method	Permanganate method
W-1	0.020	0.022
W-2	0.30	0.31
W-3	0.22	0.20
Effluent-1	0.018	0.020

Conclusions

This is a fast, reliable and accurate spectrophotometric method for the determination of manganese in silicate rocks, soils, stream sediments, minerals (sea-bed polymetallic nodules) and steel samples. Manganese can be determined in these samples with fairly good accuracy and precision. The proposed method is comparable with AAS in terms of accuracy in the determination of manganese in those samples where manganese content is very high.

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